

Alkyl derivatives, prepared by the action of alkyl halides on the sodium derivative, appear to be *S*-ethers.

The absence of thiol group in these compounds was confirmed as they could neither decolourise alcoholic solution of iodine nor could give lead salt and the absence of a thioketonic group was inferred from their incapability to react normally with phenylhydrazine in the cold with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen. Phenylhydrazine at higher temperatures reacted with these compounds with evolution of mercaptans and formation of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-ethyl-5-ketopyrazolone. On boiling with dilute acids these compounds evolved mercaptans and carbon dioxide. These facts assert the mobile nature of the sulphur atom in the β -position to the carbethoxy group.

Ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate furnished acetyl and benzoyl derivatives. The acylated products do not contain any thiol group. They react with phenylhydrazine forming symmetrical acetyl- and benzoyl-phenylhydrazine respectively and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-ethyl-5-ketopyrazolone. Thus it becomes conclusive that phenylhydrazine primarily knocked off the acyl groups and then reacted with the liberated ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate and formed the corresponding pyrazolone.

The action of Grignard's reagent supports such a structure for the acyl derivatives. The acetyl derivative, on treatment with ethylmagnesium bromide, furnished methylethylketone and ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate was regenerated.

It can safely be concluded that the effect of the thioketonic group on the second hydrogen atom of the methylene group in close proximity is exactly identical with that of the first.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate.—Ethyl ethylacetoacetate (100 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (200 c. c.) saturated with hydrochloric acid gas at 0° and sulphuretted hydrogen was slowly bubbled for 8 hours at 0°. The whole mass was then treated with excess of ice-cold water and the oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and the red oil obtained after removal of ether was diluted to three times the volume with rectified spirit. Freshly prepared lead oxide was added to the solution under constant stirring at 0°. The precipitated lead salt was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid, when an emulsion was obtained which was extracted with ether, dried and distilled after removal of the solvent. A red oil (b. p. 85°/14 mm.) was obtained in 80% yield. (Found: C, 54.9; H, 8.1; S, 18.1. $C_8H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 55.1; H, 8.04; S, 18.31 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-ethyl-5-ketopyrazolone.—Ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate (5 g.) was treated with phenylhydrazine (2.5 g.), when sulphuretted hydrogen began to evolve briskly. When the reaction was moderated the whole mass was heated on a water bath for 2 hours. The product was washed several times with petroleum ether and finally crystallised from methyl alcohol in needles, m. p. 108°. (Found: N, 13.51. $C_{12}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13.81 per cent).

Ketone hydrolysis of ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate.—Ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate (15 g.) was boiled with dilute sulphuric acid (10%, 100 c. c.) and after 5 hours when no more sulphuretted hydrogen or carbon dioxide was evolved; the aqueous residue was repeatedly extracted with ether and the liquid obtained after removal of the solvent was found to be methylpropylketone; the semicarbazone, m. p. 100°, the melting point not being depressed when mixed with an authentic specimen.

Ethyl β -ethylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate.—Molecular sodium (2.5 g.) was added under ice-cooling to ethyl ethylthioacetoacetate (20 g.) in dry benzene (50 c. c.) and after 3 hours, ethyl bromide (15% more than theoretical) was added. The whole mass was then refluxed for 6 hours on a water-bath, poured into water and the benzene layer collected. The oil obtained after removing benzene was

distilled at 95°/ 14 mm., yield 60%. (Found: C, 60·3; H, 9·1; S, 15·1. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2S$ requires C, 59·4; H, 8·9; S, 15·6 per cent).

Ethyl β -isobutylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate.—Ethyl ethylthioacetate (5 g.) dissolved in benzene (20 c. c.) was added slowly to an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (0·6 g. sodium in 10 c.c. alcohol) and after 3 hours isobutyl iodide (6 g.) was added. The oil obtained as before was distilled after removal of benzene in vacuum and the fraction, b.p. 100°/15 mm. collected, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 62·38; S, 13·6. $C_{12}H_{22}O_2S$ requires C, 62·6; S, 13·9 per cent).

Ketone hydrolysis of the alkylated products.—Ethyl β -ethylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate (10 g.) was heated with sulphuric acid (10%, 75 c.c.) and the condenser was connected to two bubblers containing alcohol. The heating was continued till no more mercaptan was detected by lead acetate paper. The alcoholic solutions were then treated with excess of alcoholic solution of iodine, diluted with water and extracted by means of ether. The oil obtained after removal of ether was identified as diethyl disulphide (b.p. 152°). (Found: S, 51·9. Calc. : S, 52·41 per cent).

Action of phenylhydrazine on alkylated products.—Ethyl β -ethylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate and phenylhydrazine were heated to boiling on the sand-bath in a test tube, the test tube being connected with an alcoholic washer. After 1 hour the alcohol in the washer was treated with excess of alcoholic solution of iodine and the oil obtained after diluting with excess of water was identified to be diethyl disulphide. The residue in the test tube after washing with petroleum ether furnished 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-ethyl-5-ketopyrazolone, m. p. 108°, the mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen was unchanged.

Ethyl β -acetylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate.—Ethyl ethylthioacetate (20 g.) was treated with molecular sodium (2·5 g.) in benzene (100 c.c.) under ice-cooling and after 3 hours acetyl chloride (10 g.) was added under vigorous shaking and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 6 hours. The solution was poured into excess of water and the benzene repeatedly washed with water. On removing the solvent the product distilled at 105°/12 mm. (Found: C, 55·1; H, 7·0; S, 14·3. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3S$ requires C, 55·5; H, 7·4; S, 14·81 per cent). The same acetyl derivative was obtained by the action of thioacetic anhydride (70 g.) and pyridine (1 c.c.) upon ethyl thioacetate (20 g.).

Ethyl β -benzoylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate.—Ethyl ethylthioacetate (20 g.) and sodium (2·5 g.) reacted with benzoyl chloride (15 g.)

in a manner similar to the preceding experiment and furnished an oil, b.p. 185°/18 mm. (Found: C, 64·1; S, 11·9. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3S$ requires C, 64·7; S, 11·60 per cent).

Action of phenylhydrazine on acetylated product.—Ethyl β -acetylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate was treated with phenylhydrazine in the cold, when the mixture gradually became warm and the mass solidified with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen. When no more sulphuretted hydrogen was evolved the product was extracted with ether and crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 125°. It is identical with acetylphenylhydrazine. (Found: N, 18·75. Calc.: N, 18·71 per cent). The ether extract left a viscous oil after removal of ether and the oil on heating on the water-bath for 3 hours furnished 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-ethyl-5-ketopyrazolone, m.p. 108°.

Action of phenylhydrazine on benzoylated product.—Ethyl β -benzoylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate was treated with phenylhydrazine, when heat was developed and the mass solidified. *sym*-Benzoylphenylhydrazine was isolated as in the previous case, m.p. 168°; the mixed m.p. with a known sample was unchanged; yield theoretical.

Action of ethylmagnesium bromide on ethyl β -acetylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate.—Ethyl β -acetylmercapto- α -ethylcrotonate (15 g.) dissolved in ether (100 c.c.) was added drop by drop over magnesium-ethyl bromide prepared by dissolving magnesium (2·5 g.) in ethyl bromide (15 g.) cooled in ice and the mixture left overnight. The granular white precipitate was filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the oil obtained was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dehydrated and distilled at 85°/14 mm. It was identified to be ethyl ethylthioacetate. (Found: S, 17·9. Calc.: S, 18·3 per cent).

The ethereal filtrate in the above experiment furnished a liquid which gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 135° identical with that of methyl-ethylketone.

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